

First records of *Cyrtarachne termitophila* Lawrence, 1952 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: The male of *Cyrtarachne termitophila* Lawrence, 1952, was described from the Democratic Republic of the Congo and is here reported for the first time from South Africa. The general morphology of the species is discussed with notes on its distribution and lifestyle. The female is still unknown.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

Cyrtarachne Thorell, 1868, belongs to the family Araneidae and currently includes more than 57 described species distributed across Africa, Asia, and parts of Oceania. It is a remarkable genus of orb-weaver spiders known for their unusual “spanning thread” webs and bird-dropping mimicry. *Cyrtarachne* is listed in the sub-family Cyrtarachninae, which includes the bolas spiders *Cladomelea* as well as the triangle-web spider *Pasilobus*.

The “spanning thread webs” they construct (Stowe, 1986) are a basic orb-web, but the web diameter, sticky spiral spacing and viscid thread diameter differ from those of the usual orb-webs. The viscid threads are studded with large droplets, which are very effective at catching prey. Each short thread between the radii is known as a spanning thread and is unique in that it breaks when prey contacts it. The prey flies into the web, gets stuck to a viscid thread, the thread breaks, and the spider pulls the prey up to the centre of the web to feed (Tanikawa *et al.*, 2014).

Research in Japan by Cartan & Miyashita (2008) found that the breaking strength, stickiness, thread diameter, and droplet diameter differ significantly from those of other members of Araneidae. They found that the viscid thread diameter was 4x and the breaking strength 7-10x stronger in *Cyrtarachne* than that of other araneids. Like bolas spiders, the adhesiveness of the viscid threads decreases to zero within a few hours. During the day, the spider rests on close-by vegetation mimicking bird droppings. Of the eight species of *Cyrtarachne* known from Africa, only one, *C. ixoides* (Simon, 1870), has so far been reported from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones, 2008).

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) large numbers of Araneidae were sampled and photographed (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Also have several known species from Africa added to the South Africa National Spider List (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). This include several Araneidae species such as *Cyrtarachne termitophila* that are here the first time recorded from South Africa.

TAXONOMY

Cyrtarachne termitophila Lawrence, 1952

Cyrtarachne termitophila Lawrence, 1952: 10 (M)

Diagnostic characters: Male. TL 2 mm. Carapace orange, darker around border (Fig. 1); as wide as long, narrower in eye region (Figs 1 & 5); with three large setae; a small seta posterior of posterior median eyes; two medially on both sides of fovea; setae sometimes lost; anterior eye row viewed from the front strongly recurved; anterior median eyes larger than the posterior median eyes, their own diameter apart; posterior row recurved; lateral eyes closely grouped (Figs 1 & 5).

Figure 1–4. *Cyrtarachne termitophila* male from Isandlwane Nature Reserve. 1. Dorsal view. 2. Ventral view. 3. Male palp. 4. Setae on the front legs. Credit: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Sternum heart-shaped (Fig. 2). Abdomen wider than long, oval; dorsal scute orange; covered with chitinous scute bordered at margin with numerous conical tubercles bearing strong black setae, some lost; sigilla indistinct in male (Figs 1 & 5) but more distinct in juvenile (Figs 9-11); abdomen ventrally with darker tint (Fig. 10). Leg I with stiff setae; tibia I in basal third on inner side with a long spine-like seta directed inwards almost at right angle to the segment (Figs 1,4 &5); Leg 1 with rows of short spinelike setae (Figs 1 & 8). Male palp large as seen from below (Figs 2–3, 6–7). Female unknown.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: DRC, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Isandlwane Nature Reserve, Dundee (-28.86, 28.21). *Limpopo:* Legalametse Nature Reserve (-24.19, 30.33).

Known distribution of *Cyrtarachne termitophila* in South Africa.

LIFESTYLE

The holotype male was sampled by Mr N. Leleup in 1949 from a termite nest in the DRC. Lawrence (1952) remarked that it is unusual for an Araneidae spider to be found in a termite nest.

The specimens in South Africa were sampled by sweeping grass in two reserves. *Cyrtarachne* species are known to construct “spanning thread webs” usually in low vegetation (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones, 2008). The male with its spikey abdomen blends in with the grasses and is therefore not easily seen.

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Figure 5–8. *Cyrtarachne termitophila* male. 5. Habitus dorsal view. 6–7. Male palp. 8. Leg I. Credits: After Lawrence (1952).

Figure 9–11. *Cyrtarachne termitophila* immature female from Legalametse Nature Reserve. 9. Dorsal view. 10. Ventral view. 11. Lateral view. Credit: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

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